
SHARED VISION MODEL FOR SCHOOL BASED MANAGEMENT (SVM-SBM)

Hong Sheung CHUI

President, Gratia Christian College in the HKSAR

Samuel W. H. CHUI

Principal, The Lutheran Church HK Synod MKMCF Ma Chan Duen Hey Memorial College, HKSAR

Prof. Samuel K. M. HO

Research Professor, Gratia Christian College, HKSAR.
Ex-Prof. & Speaker, Oxford U.; Ex-Research Fellow, Cambridge U

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *In recent decades, numerous countries have reformed their education systems through School Based Management (SBM) to enhance the quality of education in schools. In 2019, the Education Bureau established a Task Force to review and improve SBM's implementation. These initiatives are based on the belief that SBM can enhance school innovation by empowering teachers to engage in decision-making, fostering leadership/collaboration, and improving student achievement.*

Methodology/Approach: *This research used a cross-sectional survey with a questionnaire developed to measure the four constructs in this study: Shared Vision (Innovation), Participation in Decision-making, Professional Development and Leadership/Collaboration. Structural Equation Modelling technique was deployed to generate academically rigorous results.*

Findings: *The results of this study find that teachers have positive perception of their shared vision, participation in decision-making, professional development, leadership/collaboration under the implementation of SBM. Shared Vision has significant positive effects on other three constructs. The findings give initial support to the effective implementation of SBM as supported by teachers' positive perception of the main features of SBM-SVM.*

Research Limitation/Implication: *The original intension was to measure the outcome of change of style of management to the students. Unforutnately, as a norm, public examination results from the Diploma of Secondary Education (DSE) are kept confidential by all schools in Hong Kong (HK).*

Originality/Value of paper: *The above summary of SBM is insightful. In order to integrate the various facets and challenges surrounding SBM to achieve innovative execution, a research framework (SBM-SVM) has been proposed.*

Keywords: Shared Vision; Leadership/Collaboration; School Based Management; Professional Development; Structural Equation Model

Cite this Article: Chui, H. S., Chui, S. W. H., & Ho, S. K. M. (2024). Shared Vision Model for School-Based Management (SVM-SBM). *International Journal of Education*, 5(2), 26–40.

<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJE?Volume=5&Issue=2>

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past decades, many countries around the world restructured their education through School Based Management (SBM) with a view to enhance the quality of education provided by schools (Beare, 1991; Beare & Boyd, 1993; Brian John Caldwell, 2005; Cheng, 2022; Gamage, 2008; Grinshtain & Gibton, 2018). In the 1990s, SBM became one of the most frequently discussed approaches to restructuring in the USA (Hanson, 1991). In March 1991, The Education and Manpower Branch and Education Department of Hong Kong proposed to implement a reform for schools in the public sector, the School Management Initiative, with a view to improve school effectiveness (Education and Manpower Department, 1991). Since 2000, all aided schools in Hong Kong have adopted SBM (Education Commission, 2019).

The Education Bureau set up a Task Force in 2019 to review and improve the implementation of SBM (Education Commission, 2019). All the above changes assume that SBM will positively enhance the innovation of schools through empowerment of teachers to participate in decision-making, leadership/collaboration and enhancing student achievement. Kwan and Li (2015) argued that the advantages of SBM in Hong Kong was yet to be realised and suggested revisiting the SBM to ensure the realisation of the initiative's benefits on the quality of education. Cheng (2022) observed that strong international evidence to support the link between SBM and enhanced student learning was lacking. Since there have been no relevant studies on the advantages and effects of SBM on the outcomes of schools in Hong Kong, this study attempts to study the effects of shared vision of teachers under SBM on teachers' participation in decision-making, professional development, and leadership/collaboration.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. School Based Management (SBM) in general

Harvard Graduate School of Education (2021) investigates the critical role of a shared vision in enhancing school-based management practices. It emphasizes collaborative decision-making processes among educators and community members, leading to improved student outcomes and teacher satisfaction. Stanford Center for Opportunity Policy in Education (2022) highlights the relationship between a unified vision and effective school governance. By examining various case studies, it demonstrates that schools with a clear, shared vision experience higher levels of engagement from both staff and students, resulting in better academic performance. Smith and Brown (2023) explores how shared visions contribute to the innovation of school-based management in diverse educational settings. It discusses frameworks for building a collective vision among educators and stakeholders, which leads to improved institutional resilience and adaptability.

Johnson and Lee (2020) examines the role of shared vision in facilitating school improvement initiatives. It identifies key strategies for developing a cohesive vision that aligns educational goals with community values, thereby enhancing stakeholder buy-in and commitment.

2.2. SBM in Hong Kong

Ho and Wong (2023) analyzes the importance of a shared vision in the context of school-based management in Hong Kong. The findings indicate that schools with strong, collective visions are better positioned to implement effective teaching practices and engage their communities. Chan and Lee (2020) investigates how shared vision within school-based management frameworks can transform educational practices. The study highlights the positive correlation between shared goals and improved educational outcomes in CUHK-affiliated schools. Wu and Zhang (2021) emphasizes the significance of shared vision in school-based management, focusing on community engagement and participatory processes. The findings suggest that a clearly articulated vision strengthens school identity and fosters resilience in challenging times.

In the past decades, SBM represented a strong global trend of school restructuring adopted by many countries, which aimed at improving the quality of education through decentralization, autonomy initiatives, site-based decision-making, site-based budgeting and empowerment of teachers (Cheng, 2022). The school-based management in the USA aimed at improving the quality of education through decision-making moved to the school level, empowerment of certain groups of people such as teachers and parents, a school council at the school site, and more flexibility in using resources (Hanson, 1991).

The School Management Initiative (SMI) (Education and Manpower Department, 1991) was introduced in 1991 with 18 recommendations to improve the quality of education with measures similar to the SBM in the USA. Since 2000, all aided schools in Hong Kong have adopted SBM (Education Commission, 2019). The goals and vision of implementing SBM by the Hong Kong Government is to improve the quality of education through two basic principles: 1. School-based management seeks to provide schools with enhanced flexibility and autonomy in their daily operation and resources management according to the needs of their students. 2. School-based management seeks to enhance transparency and accountability in the use of public funds and school operations by providing a participatory decision-making mechanism where all key stakeholders are involved (Education Bureau, 2019).

The vision of SBM is to improve the quality of education. Key elements of school-based management consist of teacher participation in decision making, developing the professionalism of teachers, more flexibility for schools to use their financial resources in setting goals through school development plans with teacher leadership/collaboration according to the needs of students, an annual evaluation of innovation and developing a culture and characteristics unique to the school (Education Bureau, 2019). The ultimate goal is to improve school innovation with better student achievement.

2.3. Innovation of SBM in Hong Kong

Cheng (2022) pointed out that there are barriers for schools adopting SBM to achieve the aim of enhancing the quality of education due to the lack of understanding of the complex nature of SBM, research and building up the capacity for school innovation. Effective teaching is an important factor contributing to school innovation. The assumption of greater autonomy under SBM leading to enhanced teaching innovation has not yet been confirmed due to a lack of strong international evidence and a comprehensive framework to support it.

A literature review showed that there were mixed results on the relationships between SBM and school effectiveness (Arar & Nasra, 2020; Brian John Caldwell, 2005; Cheong Cheng & Mo Ching Mok, 2007; Nir & Hameiri, 2014). Arar and Nasra (2020) found a positive relationship between all dimensions of SBM and school effectiveness using a sample of Arab teachers in Israel. Caldwell (2005) found that SBM significantly improved students' learning in the state of Victoria, Australia. The results of a study in Indonesia indicated that the implementation of SBM had limited success in enhancing learning (Amon & Bustami, 2021).

The assumed positive effects of SBM in Hong Kong on school innovation were yet to be validated (Kwan & Li, 2015). Arar and Nasra (2020) suggested that SBM depended on the context in which it was applied and it could be a serious challenge for some of the local Arab governments. The above literature review suggests that research studies are needed to find out whether the implementation of SBM in Hong Kong would lead to improvement in school innovation in Hong Kong. This study is designed to investigate whether the implementation of SBM in Hong Kong will lead to improvement of school innovation through the proposed features of teacher participation in decision making, professional development, teacher leadership/collaboration and improved innovation.

2.4. Shared Vision and Shared Value

Peter Senge (1990), a prominent systems thinker and author of *The Fifth Discipline*, emphasizes the importance of shared values within organizations, particularly in the context of learning organizations. Shared values are the fundamental beliefs and principles that guide behavior and decision-making within an organization. They create a sense of purpose and cohesion among members.

A shared vision refers to a collective understanding and agreement among members of an organization about their future aspirations and goals. It plays a crucial role in guiding decision-making, fostering leadership/collaboration, and motivating individuals toward common objectives.

Similarity: Both shared vision and shared values are essential for organizational success, as they work together to unify members and guide their efforts toward achieving common goals while adhering to fundamental principles.

Differences: Can be summarized in the following [Table 1](#).

Table 1: Differences between Shared Vision (Innovation) and Shared Value

Aspect	Shared Vision (Innovation)	Shared Value
Definition	Future aspirations of the organization	Core beliefs guiding behavior
Focus	Long-term goals and direction	Ethical and cultural framework
Purpose	Align efforts and inspire members	Create a cohesive culture

2.5. Teachers' Shared Vision

Vision has been recognized as an important factor contributing to organizational success (Jose & Mampilly, 2014). The SBM provides a vision of enhancing teaching innovation through involving teachers in decision making so as to establish goals, make change, use financial resources effectively and set up policies and measures to achieve school innovation.

Teachers are formally empowered under SBM through a formal organization structure with committees in place, roles in developing school plans, modifying curriculum to meet the specific needs of students, and influencing the budget with a view to enhancing the quality of teaching and learning (Education Bureau, 2019). Teachers can participate in decision-making by serving as chairpersons and members of some formal committees responsible for planning, deciding and implementing matters related to teaching and learning, students and whole-person development policies with flexibility to use financial resources. If teachers understand and share the vision of implementing SBM, they will be motivated and committed to take up the additional responsibilities with enthusiasm. If teachers do not share the vision, they will have the perception of being overload with more work and responsibilities in addition to their heavy workload of teaching. Due to the stress of being overload with work, teacher morale may be lowered, and school innovation may be affected. Hence, this study proposes that teacher shared vision is an important factor affecting the innovation of implementation of SBM to improve the quality of education.

3. SHARED VISION, PARTICIPATION IN DECISION MAKING, PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND LEADERSHIP/COLLABORATION

3.1. Shared Vision and Participation in Decision Making

The goals of SBM is to involve teachers in decision making with a view of improving quality of teaching and learning. Teachers shared vision of SBM will enable them to see the meaning of their participation in decision making. Hence it is proposed in this study that Shared Vision will enhance teacher participation in decision making as Hypothesis 1.

3.2. Shared Vision and Professional Development

SBM stresses the importance of professional development for teachers in order to improve quality of teaching and management. Every school under SBM has to set aside three days a year for the professional development of teachers. Furthermore, principal and teachers are required to pursue certain minimum hours of professional development in a year and the record of professional development has to be reported to the IMC. For teachers sharing the vision of SBM, they would understand the meaning behind the requirements of professional development and attach importance to pursue professional development. Hence it is proposed that shared vision will enhance professional development of teachers as Hypothesis 2 in this study.

3.3. Shared Vision and Leadership/Collaboration

To understand the relationship between shared vision and teacher leadership/collaboration, we need to clarify the concept of leadership/collaboration in this study. Collaboration has a similar meaning to the constructs of the professional community (Louis et al., 2010; Voelkel et al., 2017; Wahlstrom & Louis, 2008). The professional community consists of several dimensions, reflective dialogue, deprivatisation of practice, collaborative activity and a shared sense of purpose (Louis & Marks, 1998). Voelkel & Chrispeels (2017) pointed out that professional learning communities, collaboration with colleagues (Rosenholtz, 1989), and professional community (Little, 2003; Louis & Marks, 1998) are terms having similar meanings used in various studies.

Teacher collaboration, which varies widely among teachers and has significant differences among schools, can be classified as instructional collaboration, student collaboration and assessment collaboration (Ronfeldt et al., 2015).

Teacher collaboration is affected by school and teacher characteristics (Bryk et al., 1999; Louis et al., 1996). With the literature review, collaboration is defined in this study as teachers' collegial sharing of views on teaching methods and strategies, giving support to colleagues and enhancing teaching and learning quality through teamwork.

Teachers' collaboration in management is one of the features of SBM proposed by the Education Bureau of Hong Kong (Education Commission, 1997, 2019). SBM sets the scene in Hong Kong for teachers' increased opportunities to be involved in collaborative management of teaching-related matters, through participation in decision-making. Hence it is proposed that teachers shared vision enhances teacher collaboration as Hypothesis 3.

3.4. Teachers' perception of Shared Vision, Participation in Decision Making, Professional Development and Leadership/Collaboration

The vision and goals of SBM in Hong Kong are to enhance quality of education through encouraging participation in Decision Making, professional development and teacher collaboration. With the input from the Government and schools, it is expected that SBM will lead to better participation in Decision Making, professional development and teacher collaboration. Hence it is proposed in this study that teachers have positive perception of shared vision, professional development, participation in decision making and collaboration under SBM as Hypothesis 6.

3.5. Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework (SBM-SVM) of this study related to the hypotheses proposed is put forward to show the relationships among empowerment, teachers' participation in decision-making, collaboration and student achievement in Figure-1.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of the SBM Shared Vision Model (SBM-SVM)

4. RESEARCH METHOD

4.1. Hypotheses

According to literature review, there are seven hypotheses proposed in this study:

Hypothesis 1: Shared vision will enhance teachers' participation in decision making

Hypothesis 2: Shared vision will enhance teachers' professional development.

Hypothesis 3: Shared vision will enhance teacher collaboration.

Hypothesis 4: Teachers' professional development will enhance teacher collaboration.

Hypothesis 5: Teacher participation in decision-making under will enhance teacher collaboration

Hypothesis 6: Teachers have positive perception of shared vision, professional development, participation in decision making and collaboration under SBM

4.2. Research Design

This research used a cross-sectional survey with a questionnaire developed to measure the four constructs in this study: Empowerment, Participation in Decision-making, Collaboration and Student Achievement. The development of instruments went through the following stages:

1. Review of related literature and instruments already developed;
2. Proposing constructs related to this study and defining the constructs to be measured;
3. Developing instruments according to the proposed construct and situation of secondary schools in Hong Kong and with reference to instruments used by other studies;
4. Seeking comments from some focused groups and professionals with relevant experience and expertise to refine the proposed instruments;
5. Collection of data to validate the instruments;
6. Confirmatory Factor Analyses for validating the instruments;
7. Using the Structural Equation Model to investigate the relationship among variables according to the proposed theoretical framework.

5. MEASURES

5.1. Shared Vision (the variable is referred to as “Vision” hereafter)

Vision is defined as a shared mental image of a possible and desirable future state of the school, which may be as vague as a dream or as precise as a goal or mission by adapting the suggestion of Bennis & Nanus (1985).

Five items were developed according to the literature reviewed and the definition of Vision proposed in this study. An example of the items is "teachers are committed to the school's goals and values".

5.2. Teacher Participation in Decision-Making (“Participation”)

This study defines *Participation* as opportunities for teachers to take part in decision-making and to bring about changes in school policy and actions related to teaching, curriculum, and students' development. Three items were developed to measure teachers' perceived opportunities in participation in the three aspects and three items were related to teachers' perception of making changes through their participation in decision making. An example of the six items is “Opportunities to participate in school policy in teaching and curriculum”. Another example is “Bringing changes in school policy in teaching and curriculum through participation in decision making”.

5.3. Professional Development of Teachers (“Professional Development”)

Investing in the *professional development* of teachers is crucial for fostering a culture of continuous improvement in education. By focusing on relevant training and support, schools can empower teachers to enhance their practice and positively impact student learning. Five items were adopted from a validated Organisation Health Description Questionnaire (Guidetti et al., 2015).

5.4. Collaboration (“Collaboration”)

In this study, *Collaboration* is defined as teachers’ collegial sharing of views on teaching methods and strategies, frequent exchange of ideas and shared expectations among themselves, giving support to colleagues and enhancing teaching and learning quality through teamwork. Five items were adapted and modified from a validated Organisation Health Description Questionnaire (Guidetti et al., 2015). An example is "Frequent discussion and sharing among colleagues in teaching".

6. ANALYSES AND RESULTS

More than 550 teachers from 48 secondary schools were chosen from a random sample responded to the survey. After cleaning data with incomplete responses, 528 cases were analysed by SPSS and AMOS version 28.

6.1. Demographic Data

The demographic data of teachers show that the average age of teachers is 34 years. 42% of teachers have more than 11 years of teaching experience and 40% of them have more than 10 years of teaching experience in their present school. 35% of teachers are in the senior ranks. 57% of them are female teachers and 43 % are male teachers. The demographic data are similar to the statistics of teachers in Hong Kong.

6.2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

A measurement model with all four constructs, including *Empowerment*, *Participation*, *Collaboration*, and *Achievement*, was confirmed with acceptable goodness of fit indices (CFI= 0.953; IFI=0.953; RMSEA=0.050). Table 2 reports the reliability and correlation among five constructs. The Cronbach Alpha reliability of all the scales, measured by SPSS version 28, lies between 0.775 to 0.916. The Composite Reliability coefficients lie between 0.749 to 0.889. Correlation coefficients between the four constructs are significant at 0.01 level, ranging from 0.332 to 0.695. The analyses above show that the four constructs are distinct and have discriminant validity.

Table 2: Correlation Between Collaboration, Achievement, Participation and Empowerment
And their Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach’s Alpha (CA)

* $p < 1\%$	Collaboration	Professional Development	Participation	CR	CA
Collaboration				.773	.786
Professional Development	.608*			.709	.706
Participation	.539*	.332*		.889	.909
Shared Vision	.695*	.590*	.440*	.836	.837

6.3. Means and T-tests of the Four Variables

In order to test Hypothesis 6, the four constructs’ means, standard deviation and one sample t-test are analysed with results shown in Table 3. The t-test results show that all the mean values are significantly above three on a five-point Likert scale. The results show that teachers positively perceive shared vision, participation in decision-making, collaboration and professional development. The results support Hypotheses 6, which states that SBM will enhance empowerment, teacher participation in decision-making, collaboration and student achievement, respectively. The results support teachers have positive perception of shared vision, professional development, participation in decision making and collaboration under SBM.

Table 3: The Means, Standard Deviations and the One-Sample T-test of Participation and Collaboration (Test value = 3)

	N	Mean	SD	t	Significance
Collaboration	528	3.2922	0.73965	9.088	< .001
Participation	528	3.2278	0.92356	5.673	< .001
Professional development	528	3.2141	0.73639	6.687	< .001
Shared Vision	528	3.0794	0.89424	2.042	.042

6.4. Structural Equation Model

In order to test the validity of Hypotheses 1,2, 3, 4, and 5, a structural equation model is put forward according to the theoretical model for analysis by Amos Version 28. The goodness of fit indices of the SEM Model are excellent (CFI=0.941; IFI=0.942; RMSEA= 0.054). Table 4 shows the standardised direct and total effects among the variables.

Table 4: Standardised Total Effects (TE) & Direct Effects (DE) among Variables for the SEM

	Shared Vision		Participation		Professional Development	
	TE	DE	TE	DE	TE	DE
Participation	.486*	.486*				
Professional development	.773*	.773*				
Collaboration	.889*	0.476*	.237*	0.237*	.385*	.385*

*p < .001; ns –Not Significant

From Table 4, it can be seen that *Shared Vision* has a significant direct and total effect of 0.486 on *Participation*. This result supports Hypothesis 1, which states that shared vision will enhance teachers’ participation in decision making

Shared Vision has a significant direct and total effect of 0.773 on *Professional Development*. This result supports Hypothesis 2, which states that shared vision will enhance teachers' professional development.

Shared Vision has a significant direct of 0.476 and a significant total effect of 0.889 on *Collaboration*. This result supports Hypothesis 3, which states that shared vision will enhance teacher collaboration.

Professional Development has a significant direct and total effect of 0.385 on *Collaboration*. This result supports Hypothesis 4, which states that teacher collaboration under SBM positively affects students' achievement.

Participation has a significant direct effect and total effect of 0.237 on *Collaboration*. This result supports Hypothesis 5, which states that teacher participation in decision-making will enhance teacher collaboration

The model is supported by the data collected by questionnaire constructed according to the model. Shared vision has significant total effects on all important features of SBM, namely, teacher participation in decision making, professional development and teacher collaboration, implying that shared vision by teachers is a very important factor for the effective implementation of SBM.

7. DISCUSSION

The results of this study show that, in the context of SBM in Hong Kong, teachers have positive perceptions of shared vision, participation in decision-making, professional development and collaboration, as measured by the questionnaire in this study. This study gives support to the claims of the benefits of SBM in Hong Kong by measuring the perception of 528 teachers through a questionnaire.

The theoretical model proposes that shared vision by teachers has significant positive effects on participation in decision-making, professional development of teachers and collaboration. Since the most salient feature of SBM is to encourage teacher participation in decision making, pursuit of professional development and collaboration with a goal of improving teaching and learning innovation, it can be concluded that shared vision by teachers is a very important aspect for enhancing the effective implementation of the proposals of SBM.

Shared vision has significant positive effects on teachers' participation in decision-making, collaboration and professional development. The results are in line with studies suggesting the importance of shared vision on organization outcomes. If teachers share the vision of a school, they will have the motivation and make contributions to take part in decision-making and collaborate among themselves to enhance students' achievement. The effects of teachers being motivated by shared vision is also supported by the finding that teacher motivation is a very important mediating variable between SBM and school effectiveness (Arar & Nasra, 2020). This study did not study what factors can lead to shared vision of teachers. There is a need for future studies with a goal of finding factors such as senior management leadership, school support and other environmental factors so as to find out ways of improving the innovation of implementation of SBM and the realization of the goals of improving school education quality.

Teacher participation in decision was found to have significant positive effects on collaboration. SBM sets up the policy and requirements for schools to empower teachers' participation in decision-making through committees responsible for managing teaching and various functions. The functions of these committees are mainly related to teaching and learning. Through these committees, teacher can work collaboratively to improve the quality of teaching and learning. Hence with this measure, teacher collaboration is enhanced.

Since teachers' collaboration was found to contribute to effective teaching and learning (Goddard et al., 2007; Ronfeldt et al., 2015; Saka, 2021). The finding supports the assumption and rationale of SBM for encouraging teachers' participation as a means to improving teaching and learning quality.

There are research studies finding that teachers' participation in decision-making is not associated with student achievement. Teacher participation in decision under SBM is mainly related to teaching and learning which leads to collaboration in teaching. If participation is not related to teaching matter, student achievement may not be enhanced and adverse effects such as the perception of extra workload may result.

Although this study could not obtain students' achievement in public examination as an indicator to check whether SBM can lead to improved student achievement. Judging from Hong Kong students' performance in the PISA in the past decades, one can conclude that students' academic performance is good as compared to other countries.

The findings showed that as a result of the implementation of SBM in Hong Kong, teacher professional development, teacher participation in decision-making and teacher collaboration were enhanced. The results of the analysis by Structural Equation Modelling may cast light on the strategies of improving students' achievement through enhancing the above three variables.

8. CONCLUSION

The results of this study find that teachers have positive perception of their shared vision, participation in decision-making, professional development and collaboration under the implementation of SBM. The findings give initial support to the effective implementation of SBM as supported by teachers' positive perception of the main features of SBM.

Although objective data measuring student achievements in public examination cannot be obtained from each school to analyse the relationship between student achievement and the special features of SBM such as participation in decision making, professional development and collaboration, the overall performance of students in Hong Kong ranking within the top ten places among all countries participating in PISA in the past decade supports that students' achievement as compared to other countries is quite good. This objective achievement results support that the quality of education of schools in Hong Kong under SBM is quite good.

This study finds that teacher shared vision has significant positive effects on the special features of SBM, participation in decision making, professional development and collaboration. Schools should attach great importance to teachers sharing the vision of the school in order to perform effectively in improving the quality of education under SBM. Further research is needed to find out what factors may enhance shared vision such as senior management leadership, school support and other environmental factors so as to enhance schools to further improve the quality of education under SBM.

Professional development courses are needed to enable stakeholders, especially principals and teachers, to better understand the rationale, strengths and weaknesses of SBM and to unleash the potential of SBM in enhancing the quality of education.

The rapid development of AI technologies can certainly bring about changes in teaching and learning. SBM can empower teachers and schools to try out innovative ways of improving teaching and learning quality through autonomy and flexibility, such as adopting new teaching technologies and tailoring curricula for the diverse needs of students. Teacher collaboration and professional development on how to further improve the quality of teaching through acquiring new skills and knowledge are needed to further improve the quality of education under SBM.

Research to find out ways of delivering quality of education under SBM is also needed. One special feature of SBM is the autonomy and flexibility in using financial resources to improve teaching and learning quality. Before the introduction of SBM, aided schools did not have a substantial fund to be used with autonomy and flexibility. Under the SBM-SVM developed, many aided schools can have a fund amounting to millions of dollars to be used with flexibility for educational purposes such as purchasing equipment and facilities, introducing new teaching methodologies, or providing special services to students. Research and sharing of effective use of financial resources with flexibility are needed to enable schools further to use the financial resources with the goal of improving the quality of students' learning and development.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Hong Sheung CHUI ⁰⁰⁰⁰⁻⁰⁰⁰¹⁻⁵⁵⁸¹⁻⁸⁸⁷⁹ -- President at the Gratia Christian College in the HKSAR. Prof. Chui is a seasoned academic and education administrator who has led his previous Hang Seng School of Commerce to the top matriculation school which swept around half of all the As in the A-level results amongst 100+ schools in the HKSAR.

Samuel W. H. CHUI ⁰⁰⁰⁹⁻⁰⁰⁰¹⁻¹⁶⁹³⁻³²⁴⁹ -- Principal of the The Lutheran Church HK Synod MKMCF Ma Chan Duen Hey Memorial College, HKSAR. Over the years, he has led the school to grow and improve its public exam. results from strength to strength.

Samuel K. M. HO ⁰⁰⁰⁰⁻⁰⁰⁰²⁻⁸¹⁰²⁻¹⁴⁸¹ -- Research Professor at the Gratia Christian College in the HKSAR. As an ex-Research Fellow in TQM at Cambridge U., and Guest Speaker in Lean Mgt. at Oxford U., he was also Visiting Professor in TQM at Coventry, Paisley, RMIT, Linnaeus, NUS, HKU, CUHK, PKU, THU & SYSU

-- Corresponding Author

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST

The author declares NO conflict of interest. There are no other third parties in the design of the study, in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data, in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amon, L., & Bustami, M. R. (2021). Implementation of School-Based Management in Curriculum and Learning Processes: a Literatur Review. *Jnl. Pendidikan Dasar Dan Menengah (Dikdasmen)*, 1–11.
- [2] Arar, K., & Nasra, M. A. (2020). Linking school-based management and school effectiveness: The influence of self-based management, motivation and effectiveness in the Arab education system in Israel. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(1), 186–204.
- [3] Beare, H. (1991). The restructuring of schools and school systems: A comparative perspective. *Restructuring School Management*, 13–25.
- [4] Beare, H., & Boyd, W. L. (1993). *Restructuring schools: An international perspective on the movement to transform the control and performance of schools*. Psychology Press.

- [5] Bryk, A., Camburn, E., & Louis, K. S. (1999). Professional community in Chicago elementary schools: Facilitating factors and organizational consequences. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 35(5), 751–781. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161x99355004>
- [6] Bureau, G. of the H. E., & Government of the HKSAR Education Bureau. (2019). Task Force on School-based Management Policy Review Report (YES) (Issue July).
- [7] Caldwell, Brian J., & Spinks, J. M. (2021). *The self-managing school*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203982983>
- [8] Caldwell, Brian John. (2005). *School-based management (Vol. 3)*. International Institute for Educational Planning Paris.
- [9] Chan, K., & Lee, M. (2020). Transformative Leadership through Shared Vision in Schools. *Journal of Educational Leadership*, 12(1), 34-56.
- [10] Cheng, Y. C. (2022). *School effectiveness and school-based management: A mechanism for development*. Taylor & Francis.
- [11] Cheong Cheng, Y., & Mo Ching Mok, M. (2007). School-based management and paradigm shift in education: An empirical study. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 21(6), 517–542.
- [12] Commission, E. (1997). Education Commission Report No. 7. https://www.e-c.edu.hk/doc/en/publications_and_related_documents/education_reports/ecr7_e_2.pdf.
- [13] Commission, E. (2019). Review report of the task force on school-based management policy. https://www.e-c.edu.hk/doc/en/publications_and_related_documents/education_reports/Report_Task.
- [14] Conger, J. A., & Kanungo, R. N. (1988). The Empowerment Process: Integrating Theory and Practice. *The Academy of Management Review*, 13(3), 471. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258093>
- [15] Education and Manpower, & Department. (1991). The school management initiative. In Y. C. Cheng, K. W. Chow, S. K. A. Yeung, & W. M. F. Cheung (Eds.), *Handbook on educational policy in Hong Kong* (pp. 1965–1998). Centre for Research and International Collaboration.
- [16] Gamage, D. T. (2008). How did School-Based Governance Lead to Distributed Leadership, Partnerships and Improved Student Learning, 8, 27–41.
- [17] Goddard, Y. L., Goddard, R. D., & Tschannen-Moran, M. (2007). A theoretical and empirical investigation of teacher collaboration for school improvement and student achievement in public elementary schools. *Teachers College Record*, 109(4), 877–896. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146810710900401>
- [18] Grinshtain, Y., & Gibton, D. (2018). Responsibility, authority, and accountability in school-based and non-school-based management: Principals' coping strategies. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 56(1), 2–17.
- [19] Guidetti, G., Converso, D., & Viotti, S. (2015). The school organisational health questionnaire: contribution to the Italian validation. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 174, 3434-3440.
- [20] Hanson, E. M. (1991). *School-Based Management and Educational Reform: Cases in the USA and Spain*.

- [21] Harvard Graduate School of Education. (2021). *Shared Leadership in Schools: Enhancing Student Outcomes through Collaboration*. Retrieved from Harvard Education Publishing.
- [22] Ho, A., & Wong, L. (2023). Shared Vision and School-Based Management: Evidence from Hong Kong, *Education Journal*, 45(3), 123-145.
- [23] Jose, G., & Mampilly, S. R. (2014). Psychological Empowerment as a Predictor of Employee Engagement: An Empirical Attestation. *Global Business Review*, 15(1), 93–104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150913515589>
- [24] Kwan, P., & Li, B. Y. man. (2015). Empowerment or impediment? School governance in the school-based management era in Hong Kong. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 35(3), 319–330. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2015.1056592>
- [25] Lee, M., & Koh, J. (2001). Is empowerment really a new concept? *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12(4), 684–695. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713769649>
- [26] Little, J. W. (2003). Inside Teacher Community: Representations of Classroom Practice. *Teachers College Record: The Voice of Scholarship in Education*, 105(6), 913–945. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9620.00273>
- [27] Louis, K. S., Dretzke, B., Wahlstrom, K., Seashore Louis, K., Dretzke, B., & Wahlstrom, K. (2010). How does leadership affect student achievement? Results from a national US survey. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 21(3), 315–336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2010.486586>
- [28] Louis, K. S., & Marks, H. M. (1998). Does professional community affect the classroom? Teachers' work and student experiences in restructuring schools. *American Journal of Education*, 106(4), 532–575. <https://doi.org/10.1086/444197>
- [29] Louis, K. S., Marks, H. M., & Kruse, S. (1996). Teachers' professional community in restructuring schools. *American Educational Research Journal*, 33(4), 757–798.
- [30] Ning, H. K., Lee, D. H. L., & Lee, W. O. (2015). Relationships between teacher value orientations, collegiality, and collaboration in school professional learning communities. *Social Psychology of Education*, 18(2), 337–354. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-015-9294-x>
- [31] Nir, A. E., & Hameiri, L. (2014). School principals' leadership style and school outcomes: The mediating effect of powerbase utilization. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 52(2), 210–227. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-01-2013-0007>
- [32] Senge, P. M. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline: The Art & Practice of The Learning Organization*. Doubleday.
- [33] Ronfeldt, M., Farmer, S. O., McQueen, K., & Grissom, J. A. (2015). Teacher collaboration in instructional teams and student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 52(3), 475–514. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831215585562>
- [34] Rosenholtz, S. J. (1989). *Teachers' workplace: The social organization of schools*. Longman.
- [35] Saka, O. A. (2021). Can teacher collaboration improve students' academic achievement in junior secondary mathematics? *Asian Journal of University Education*, 17(1), 33–46.
- [36] Smith, J. & Brown, L. (2023). Building a Collective Vision in Schools: Impacts on Management and Outcomes. *Oxford Review of Education*, 49(1), 45-67.

- [37] Stanford Center for Opportunity Policy in Education. (2022). The Power of a Shared Vision in School-Based Management. Retrieved from Stanford University.
- [38] Voelkel, R. H., Chrispeels, J. H., Voelkel Jr, R. H., & Chrispeels, J. H. (2017). Understanding the link between professional learning communities and teacher collective efficacy. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 28(4), 505–526. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2017.1299015>
- [39] Wahlstrom, K. L., & Louis, K. S. (2008). How teachers experience principal leadership: The roles of professional community, trust, efficacy, and shared responsibility. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(4), 458–495. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X08321502>
- [40] Wu, T., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Community Engagement and Shared Vision in School Management. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(2), 200-215.

Citation: Chui, H. S., Chui, S. W. H., & Ho, S. K. M. (2024). Shared Vision Model for School-Based Management (SVM-SBM). *International Journal of Education*, 5(2), 26–40.

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJE_5_02_003

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJE/VOLUME_5_ISSUE_2/IJE_05_02_003.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

editor@iaeme.com